

D8.2

Report on Congress

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→Communication, Dissemination
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→VUA Netherlands

MIDA-training-week

28th of October-1st of November 2019,
Utrecht, Netherlands

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(coordinator WP 8; involved in WP 4)

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In the last week of October 2019 MIDA organised its first training event after the hiring of our 15 ESR's. All ESR's were present except for two (one having issues with the permit, and the other one has only recently been appointed).

The program in Utrecht was set up with a number of goals in mind.

Introduction and information

First goal

The first was to welcome and inform the ESRs and to introduce them to the members of the MIDA-team; to provide them with additional information about the goal of the whole MIDA project and the training program throughout the coming years; to inform them about ethical issues around the project and issues of data-management and data storage; and to provide technical information and practicalities with regard to the MIDA-logistics.

This was done on Monday ('introduction work packages') and Tuesday ('ethic and responsibilities in human sciences'). The larger part of the program on Wednesday, Thursday and Friday was devoted to data management, questions about the epistemological underpinnings and consequences of the different projects, and publication and output strategies. This was organised by our partners, the 'Leiden University Centre of Digital Scholarship' and 'Brill Publishers'. There were a number of speakers addressing the manifold aspects of digitisation in research and data collection (for an overview,

see the Utrecht program). In addition, there was a session planned about the 'personal career development plan', a logic and necessary topic at the start of the research. On Thursday morning the entire training program of MIDA in the next years was presented and discussed. It provided the ESRs not only with the necessary information about their own training program, but also about what else there is to offer. The MIDA-team encourages the ESRs, if they can afford it time-wise, to do more training beyond their own program.

Research, ESRs and synergy

Second goal

The second goal was to bring together the ESRs and to initiate the building of an academic community. One of the most important aims of MIDA is to continuously develop and enhance the internal consistency of the entire project. There are five research WPs based on five conceptual and thematic foci. In each of the five WPs, there are three ESRs working at their individual projects and following their individual research-specific training. At the same time the ESRs of each WP are supposed to work together as much as possible and to constantly reflect on, elaborate and sophisticate the overall theme of the work package.

Although the theme of each work package was formulated in the project application, the logic of the program implies that this has to be substantiated throughout the course of the program. In addition, there are also cross connections and overlaps between two or more WPs. In order to accomplish, at the end of the MIDA-program, optimal coherence and clear common conclusions and outputs, cross-cooperation, developing ideas and results across individual research projects, is essential and one of the main priorities of the whole MIDA-project. Therefore, the ESRs will be given assignments on each training occasion, to substantiate this coherence. This was done on Monday where each of the ESRs introduced her/himself with a short pitch of their research and a Q&A session. On

Tuesday in the session 'Consistencies and Synergies of WPs' the ESRs of each of the five WPs were asked as a team to prepare their first view on what the theme of their WP is about, what cross-connections they see, and what ideas they have about how this should be developed. Later on, they had to present this in a poster-presentation. This was a very successful activity and considered very useful by the ESRs. As MIDA-team we decided to schedule this in all subsequent plenary training meetings, beginning with the next Springschool in Catania, Italy in March 2020. Since that school will be organised by the participants in WP 1 (Narratives of the Self) and WP 4 (Contested Authority and Knowledge Production), the two teams will also prepare a common presentation.

Key notes

Third goal

The third goal of the Utrecht program was to convey knowledge. Since the event in Utrecht was organised parallel with the Autumn School of the Netherlands Interuniversity institute for the Study of Islam (NISIS), and since the theme of the Autumn School was digital humanities, the program was scheduled in such a way that a considerable number of the keynotes could be attended by the ESRs.

Additional activities

MIDA plans to provide an integrated program of dissemination and communication of the proceedings and outcomes of the project. PS-Media in Berlin, one of the partner organisations, has started to record MIDA activities from the launch of MIDA in Grenada in March 2019 onward and continued during the Utrecht meeting with the making of two short clips, one in which the ESRs are presented, and one where the MIDA program is briefly presented by prof. dr. Pascal Buresi, MIDA project manager, and prof. dr. Thijl Sunier, coordinator of WP 8. These clips were published on YouTube.

In Utrecht the first official meeting of the Supervisory Board was organised on Monday. The SB acts as the management of MIDA. At this meeting

two of the four members of the Advisory Board were present, prof. dr. Heffner and prof. dr. Van Steenberg.